

Temple of Һaldi (Ayanis)

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The Temple of Һaldi located in Ayanis is one of the best examples of an Urartian susi temple. It is also the most comprehensively excavated and published Urartian religious building. It was built during the reign of Rusa son of Argišti, the last Urartian ruler who left a tangible mark both in the archaeological record and in the textual one. The temple complex measures 30 x 30 m, divided by the rest of the settlement by mudbrick walls. Inside the open courtyard, the susi temple measures 13 x 13 m and abuts the eastern courtyard wall. In front of the temple, four monumental pillars supported a portico around the northern, western and southern walls. Outside the courtyard, additional building connected to the temple complex have been excavated on the northern and eastern sides. The temple itself has a standard rectangular structure, with buttressed corners. The lower structure of the temple was made of andesite blocks, placed directly onto bedrock, and supporting mudbrick walls of a considerable, albeit unknown, height. Inside the cella, the floor was covered with alabaster slabs, and the andesite blocks were carved and inlaid with a softer stone. The motifs included winged figures and animals, rosettes, plants, and geometrical designs. A long monumental inscription, divided into eight sections is carved either side of the entrance to the temple, and on the two walls of the short corridor leading to the cella. Although probably in use for less than half a century, the Ayanis temple is the final stage in the evolution of Urartian cultic buildings. There is little variation in susi temples once set in this form by Minua at the end of the 9th century BCE. However, with Rusa son of Argišti we see decorative elements previously unknown, and we find the temple at a centre of a complex on which we have little information from other sites.

Date Range: 680 BCE - 650 BCE

Region: Ayanis fortress (ancient Rusahinili Eidurukai)

Region tags: Turkey

Armenian highlands, eastern shore of Lake Van

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Çilingiroğlu, A. & Salvini, M. (2001) Ayanis I: Ten Years' Excavations at Rusahinili Eiduru-Kai 1989-1998, Istituto per gli studi micenei ed egeo-anatolici CNR, Rome.
- Source 2: Çilingiroğlu A. (2005) Ritual Ceremonies in the Temple Area of Ayanis, in A. Çilingiroğlu & G. Darbyshire (eds.) Anatolian Iron Ages 5. The Proceedings of the Fifth Anatolian Iron Ages Colloquium held at Van 6-10 August 2001, British Institute of Archaeology at Ankara, Monograph No. 31, Ankara, pp.

31-37.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XN5EhdcNzZg>

– Source 1 Description: Online presentation of the latest Ayanis discoveries, from the current director of the excavation project, Prof. Dr. Mehmet Işıklı of the Atatürk University. It was part of a seminar series organised by the Center for Ancient Mediterranean and Near Eastern Studies (CAMNES).

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

– Illicit

Notes: Illicit excavations were common prior to the 1960s, when artefacts originating from the site found their way to the Van Museum. At that point the General Directorate of Museums in Ankara hired a guard, a move which prevented widespread looting.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1989 - ongoing

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Ayanis Castle excavation project

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The site is located 300 to the east of the shore of Lake Van.

– Water source

Notes: There is a spring located a short distance to the north west of the site, which is still in use by the modern communities present in the area.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Clearing

– Other [specify]: The bedrock was exposed and prepared prior to the start of construction. The walls are placed directly on top of the bedrock, which was carved in places in order to create flat surfaces or steps to support the walls. Cracks and fissures in the bedrock which were not carved out were filled with small stones.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Plantings

Notes: The cuneiform inscription carved on the temple walls mentions an orchard and a vineyard being planted at the site, as well as the establishment of a grain field.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: It is difficult to establish to what degree Urartu was an urban society. Nevertheless, the temple is located within a newly constructed settlement, which consisted of a elevated fortress and a vast lower town.

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The temple is located at the highest point of the citadel, which is also at the centre of the mound.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: The susi temple at the centre of the sacred area of the fortress.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

Notes: The area of the temple was prepared in advance, with the bedrock altered in order to accommodate the construction.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

- Sacrificial
- Worship

↳ Worship:

- Other [specify]: Urartian worship practices are not well understood.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

- Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

- Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

- Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

- Burned

Notes: There are two separate fire events, with one phase of reconstruction in between.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

- Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Notes: Although it cannot be excluded, there is no clear evidence of a battle, either as the result of pillage or war.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

- Natural phenomena

Notes: It is likely that at least one of the recorded conflagrations was the result of a powerful earthquake.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

- Yes

- ↳ In antiquity
- Once

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: Haldi

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

- ↳ Specify
 - King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Susi temples are found in every major royal Urartian settlement and fortress. It is more likely the choice of the place in its wider meaning was not motivated by religious reasons.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The susi temple is built inside a courtyard, surrounded by portico walls, with additional buildings on the other side.

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The temple complex is located on top of a rock spur.

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 169

Notes: 13x13m

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence for object being hanged on the walls of the temple complex, mostly weapons.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: The painting technique is not clear.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are traces of figures painted in blue and brown paint, however we cannot say who is represented.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is evidence of a blue painted dado on the west wall of the temple complex, with the rest of the wall painted white. On the white section there are traces of geometric designs, together with the already mentioned traces of figures.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Inscriptions are present on the cella walls, however it is difficult to judge if among their functions they also had a decorative one.

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Intaglio - the andesite blocks of the cella are carved and inlaid with a softer stone, softer stone which was painted and incised.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No
- ↳ Humans
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– No

↳ Are they sky deity:
– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:
– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:
– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:
– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:
– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:
– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: There is no evidence from anywhere in the Urartian state of statues representing Haldi.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Animal sacrifices are an important part of Urartian religion, however we do not know where the sacrifices took place.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: There are ceremonial weapons, highly decorated, dedicated by the Urartian ruler. It is likely other objects were offered, as large numbers of unused arrows and spear heads were also recovered from specific areas of the temple courtyard.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Notes: There is no indication in the Urartian texts of divination being a part of their beliefs and practices.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: The presence of several hearths in the temple courtyard, and the thick layers of soot on the walls closest to them, could suggest that regular rituals occurred. There are also strong indications of

libations being part of the rituals, together with the already mentioned weapon dedications. However, we have no indication on the scale and frequency of these rituals.

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: Field does not know.
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Field does not know.
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unfortunately we do not have any information about Urartian religious specialists. Their existence and presence at the temple is possible, however we have no evidence of it from the limited data available.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: A few clay tablets and bullae which hint at the existence of a bureaucratic system where recovered at Ayanis, however they do not come from the temple area.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No